

GLOBAL SEA LEVEL MEASUREMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The sea level along the east coast of the United States from Maine to Florida, as determined from long-term (50-100 years) measurements using conventional coastal tide gauges leveled to nearby geodetic bench marks, is apparently rising at a rate of between 1 mm/year to 4 mm/year. There are also some indications that the overall rate of rise may have increased in recent decades. Trends of this nature are also speculated to occur on a global basis. Given the persistence of the trend over decades, many coastal communities and shore installations are likely to be seriously threatened. Unfortunately, the nature and quality of existing sea level measurements make interpretations and predictions highly speculative and any overall response strategy is, therefore, difficult. The existing measurements only provide a rise of sea level relative to land. Considering geological phenomena (including positive and negative glacial rebound, land subsidence, and earthquake motions) along with nongeologic ones (rising atmospheric concentration of CO₂ and other trace gases), the analysis of sea level data becomes significantly complex and determining its temporal and spatial domains is a scientific and technological challenge. The major objective of a program effort described by National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) will be to determine the individual contributions and nature of major large-scale land motions and oceanographic effects on the measured global sea level signature.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The sea level along the East Coast of the United States from Maine to Florida, as determined from long-term (50-100 years) measurements using conventional coastal tide gauges leveled to nearby geodetic bench marks, is apparently

rising at a rate of between 1 mm/year to 4 mm/year (reference - Aubrey and Emery, 1983). There are some indications that the overall rate of rise may have increased in recent decades, even though the variability within any decade at a particular location is quite high. The profile of this relative sea level rise as a function of latitude (Figure 1) can be approximated by three roughly linear segments from (a) southern Florida to Cape Hatteras, (b) Cape Hatteras to Cape Cod, (c) Cape Cod to Eastport, Maine. While the vertical changes are small, these are greatly amplified in terms of the horizontal motion of the shoreline inland along relatively flat beach and shore areas, so that amplifications of 10 - 1,000 to 1 are common. On a gently sloping coastal plain, such as is found in Florida, amplifications greater than 10,000 to 1 exist. Given the persistence of the trend over many decades, many coastal communities and shore installations are likely to be seriously threatened by the early part of the next century. The problem is seriously compounded by the positive feedback effects of coastal erosion and storm surge potential.

Unfortunately, the nature and quality of the existing sea level measurements make interpretations and predictions highly uncertain and any overall response in terms of planning, or a systematic technical approach becomes difficult. In the first place, the measurements only provide a determination of the relative rise of the sea compared to the land. We know that the land is moving vertically even along the relatively geologically "stable" East Coast, both locally due to ground water removal and on a larger scale due to glacial rebound effects. Much of the area may be subject to other, less certain tectonic influences, e.g., historical earthquakes in South Carolina. Long term lateral shifts of the Gulf Stream also can affect sea level measurements along a substantial portion of the Southeastern Coast.

There may be a global component of sea level rise, the "eustatic rise," due to a postulated global warming trend produced by rising atmospheric concentrations of CO₂ and other trace gases resulting from fossil fuel combustion and other activities of man. Natural variability of the atmospheric constituents may be another, even dominant, factor. There also is evidence that major variability of sea level on the time scale of several or more decades exists, and is related to major global climate changes involving the large scale atmospheric pressure systems and wind fields. The relatively wide continental shelves of the East Coast are also probably responding to the increased dynamic loading by the oceans resulting from the end of the last ice age.

In terms of coastal planning, land use strategies and direct engineering solutions, it is important to be able to identify the magnitude and time-scales of the large scale oceanographic and geological effects and to distinguish these from the purely local signals. A groin or a sea wall may deal with a purely local problem, but if most of the problem is due to large scale regional or global effects of some kind, local engineering and public works solutions are apt to have limited value. Even when they may be warranted, such public works are 50-100 year, multi-million dollar investments that could be realized as totally inadequate in a decade or so, if an accelerating global trend is involved. Coastal policies cannot be effective with such a wide range of possibilities and wide uncertainties concerning the basic nature, geographic and temporal extent, and magnitude of the problem.

Before a national or global effort of sea level monitoring is conducted, small scale experiments are proposed to provide valuable indication of the measurements, techniques, and procedures. The Sea Level Experiment for the East Coast (SLEEC) is proposed as a significant scientific and engineering effort intended to implement a system that will provide the critical information on the nature of the sea level rise along the economically important east coast of the United States. Basically, we want to know if the sea is rising and/or if the land is sinking, by how much, and over what kind of time scales. This information is essential for the subsequent formulation of an effective regional and national policy regarding these problems.

2.0 OBJECTIVE

The major objective of the SLEEC effort will be to determine the individual contributions and nature of major large scale land motion and oceanographic effects to the profile of observed relative sea level rise for the East Coast of the United States (Figure 1). The fundamental question to be answered is whether the rising of the sea surface or the sinking of the land provides the dominant influence on the presently observed relative sea level rise. SLEEC would also provide the prototype system and essential

component of a world-wide network designed to address the broadest concerns of global sea level change and change in the global climate system in general.

3.0 GENERAL EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The overall approach of the SLEEC program will be to deploy selected hardware and make additional observations that supplement existing NOAA tides/sea level and geodetic programs and thereby develop a working system to provide the required sea level data. As previously noted, the sea level experiment (SLEEC), in turn, would provide the major regional component and operational prototype for a projected ocean basin and global sea level measurement system.

Based on current knowledge, it is estimated that we may be able to separate the sea level and land signals, in an average sense, for the whole east coast, after about 3 years.

Producing "hard" scientific numbers capable of resolving local effects and supporting analysis directed at interpreting causal mechanisms will probably require 5-10 years of operation. In fact, since SLEEC will provide a new class of measurements capable of resolving a more absolute sea level change for the first time rather than relative sea level change (sea level relative to the land), and at an accuracy never before achieved even for the relative values, we can expect that many new things will be observed and questions opened that will tend to require even longer operations of the SLEEC system.

4.0 TECHNICAL METHOD

The main components of the SLEEC system that will be extended and integrated are: (1) the Very-long Base Line Interferometry (VLBI) system and operations of NOAA's National Geodetic Survey Division (NGS); (2) the Global Positioning System (GPS) based geodetic survey operations of NGS; (3) the coastal water levels stations of NOAA's National Water Levels Observation Network (NWLON) operated by the National Ocean Service (NOS), Sea and Lake Levels Branch (SLLB), including a new group of "master" sea level stations employing advanced water levels measurement and data acquisition technology; (4) ancillary measurement systems colocated with the new "master" sea level stations that will provide in-situ oceanographic and meteorological information; and (5) Atlantic islands (Bermuda and the Bahamas) based sea level and oceanographic operations undertaken by NOAA's Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research (OAR) with NOS.

The VLBI and GPS systems and operations provide the core of the "land motion" component of SLEEC, while the NWLON and Atlantic islands based operations provide the core of the "relative sea level rise" component of SLEEC.

4.1 GEODETIC OPERATIONS

Both vertical land motion and sea surface position will be monitored relative to an ultra-precise absolute geodetic reference system based on VLBI and GPS technologies. The VLBI concept employs, for each baseline, two radio telescopes simultaneously observing the same extra-galactic radio source. The wave fronts of the electro-magnetic emissions from those enormously distant astronomical sources arrive at the radio telescopes as plane waves. A given wave front will arrive at each observatory at slightly different times, dependent on the overall geometry. Each observatory is electronically linked, including precise atomic clocks and sophisticated electronics capable of measuring the arrival time of an individual wave front at each observatory. In this way, the pair of observatories operates as a classical (radio) interferometer and simple geometric considerations allow determination of the vector (horizontal and vertical components) baseline between the pair of observatories. In practice, fixed or mobile antenna systems can serve as the basis for a given radio observatory.

A number of sources of systematic errors must be dealt with. At the present time, the refraction effects produced by atmospheric water vapor are the chief remaining error source limiting the application of existing VLBI systems for SLEEC. However, water vapor radiometers now exist that are capable of providing the basis for the required correction.

The GPS system uses portable ground-based radio receivers to "observe" the coded radio transmissions from a series of precisely positioned spacecraft in earth orbit. The reference satellites and orbits provide a geocentric reference system, relative to which the local position of ground-based GPS receivers can be calculated. The usual application of the GPS system employs a single receiver, whose position is determined from timing, range and range-rate calculations using the coded transmissions. However, SLEEC operations will principally employ another application of the GPS system.

By simultaneously operating two GPS receivers a relatively short distance apart (about 50 km), the system provides what amounts to a short baseline radio interferometric system, analogous in principal, to the VLBI systems. Here, the satellite radio transmissions take the place of the distant extra-galactic radio source. Water vapor refraction effects again provide the most serious error source limiting the use of GPS in the "differential" mode (i.e., two GPS receivers used as a short baseline interferometer) for SLEEC. However, the same water vapor radiometer (WVR) technology applicable to VLBI can support the GPS operations for SLEEC. The basic concept for the SLEEC GPS operations will be to use a pair of GPS receivers to differentially "step" along traverse lines connecting the main VLBI reference stations and a series of tide gauge/

sea level stations along the coast. Actually, the GPS links to the sea level stations via the individual physical "bench marks" which are conventionally leveled between the tide gauge and its shoreside references.

The VLBI observatories provide a globally distributed system of ground reference stations positioned with respect to the "fixed" stars. Colocated operations with satellite laser ranging systems at selected VLBI stations provide positions relative to the geocenter, most suitable for the GPS operations. The VLBI/GPS operations will allow the monitoring of absolute motions of a series of ground-based bench marks, including the sea level station reference bench marks, in the geocentric reference frame. Since the sea level stations provide a measure of the vertical component of motion of the sea surface relative to the land, the simple operation of subtraction of the vertical component of absolute land motion from the relative sea level as determined by the tide gauge measurements provides the true or absolute rise of the sea surface at that point, measured in a geocentric reference frame. Moreover, repeating the process at other sea level stations determines the true local sea level rise at those locations in the same global reference frame. Hence, true sea level rise profiles along coastlines can be determined over large regions, such as the East Coast, and, eventually, the globe.

The foundation or anchor points for the land-based absolute geodetic reference system will be three VLBI observatories along the East Coast of the United States located at: (1) The Richmond VLBI Observatory, operated by NGS and the U.S. Naval Observatory; (2) The Westford VLBI Observatory, operated by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) under contract to NGS in Westford, Massachusetts; and (3) The Maryland Point VLBI Observatory, located at Maryland Point, Maryland, near Washington, D.C., and operated by the Naval Research Laboratory.

NGS has procured two advanced water vapor radiometers (WVR) for permanent operations at Richmond and Westford observatories, bringing these substations within the operational accuracy of ± 1 cm for a single measurement required for SLEEC. A mobile WVR will also be required for the Maryland Point observatory. These observatories will provide the baseline anchor points for the differential GPS operations which will be the second component of the integrated geodetic operations supporting the SLEEC program.

SLEEC will involve establishing GPS traverse lines between Richmond, FL; Maryland Point, MD; and Westford, MA, with GPS station points at about 50-100km intervals. The line will be continued beyond Westford as far as Eastport Maine, so that about 30-60 GPS station points will be involved. Two GPS receivers will be marched along the traverse in a "leap-frog" fashion so that the entire coast would be

covered at 1 to 2 month intervals, while the Westford, Richmond, and Maryland Point time series are continued uninterrupted. The major GPS observations will be conducted as far as possible in conjunction with other NGS operations.

The 50-100km spacing of the GPS station points will be optimized for tie-ins to the coastal sea level gauges. GPS tie-ins to certain "master" sea level stations to be established at key locations along the East Coast will be mandatory (see Table 1).

Table 1. Proposed East Coast Master Sea Level Stations

<u>Station Location</u>
Miami, FL
Lake Worth, FL
Charleston, SC
Duck, NC
Hampton Roads, VA
Atlantic City, NJ (or Lewes, DE)
New York, NY
Newport, RI (or Providence, RI)
Boston, MA
Portland, ME
Eastport, ME

The segments of the reference baseline from Richmond, Florida to Maryland Point, Maryland, and from Maryland to Westford, Massachusetts are each about 1500km long. It is now well established that baselines of this length can be determined to within a few centimeters, using relatively short time series from existing VLBI systems. Much of the remaining error is known to be caused by radio refraction effects from atmospheric water vapor. It is expected that application of the new WVR systems will remove most of this remaining systematic error effect. Consequently, the expectation is that the baselines will shortly be measured to the +1cm level for a single measurement series. Much of the remaining error is expected to be random in nature, so that statistical processing of long time series of baseline measurements will allow use of the baseline to monitor millimeter per year magnitude trends in the vertical component of the baseline vectors, required by SLEEC.

The operational limitations on the length of the baselines that can be determined to the same level of accuracy using GPS systems in differential mode has not been determined. The 50-100km GPS baselines planned for SLEEC are conservative values; there are indications that GPS measurements of the baselines may be ultimately good to this +1cm level over hundreds of kilometers. This uncertainty in the operational limits for the GPS baselines also translates into corresponding uncertainty in the total error budget for differential "stepping" process using two GPS units "leap-frogging" between the VLBI anchor points. If the GPS

performance allows steps on the order of 100km or so, then the 1500km between the VLBI anchor points will allow the total error budget to stay within the SLEEC requirements. However, in the event that the GPS limits turn out to be more pessimistic, the 1500km distance may turn out to be excessive.

In order to provide both a means of assessing the operational limits of the GPS baselines and to allow for the "pessimistic" contingency in SLEEC (i.e., shorter VLBI baselines between anchor points are required), NGS is planning to determine two additional VLBI reference points roughly mid-way along each of the major 1500km baselines. These points will be located in North Carolina and New York State and will be determined as part of the NGS National Crustal Motion Network program. NGS is planning to measure the position of the North Carolina station using a mobile VLBI system. This will be conducted prior to transporting the mobile VLBI unit to Bermuda. The Bermuda operations will provide a common reference for the sea level measurements planned there in support of the climate program including the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE), the Tropical Ocean-Global Atmosphere Experiment (TOGA), NASA's radar alti-metric satellite mission, Ocean Topography Experiment (TOPEX), as well as SLEEC. On the way back from Bermuda, the VLBI station point in New York State will be determined using the same mobile system. If the GPS traverses indicate the need for these intermediate VLBI reference points for the SLEEC effort, then NGS will schedule periodic mobile VLBI operations to monitor their position through the duration of the SLEEC effort. The need for the intermediate mobile VLBI stations will be evaluated as part of SLEEC operations. The results using the four intermediate baseline segments will be analyzed and compared with the results derived from just the two longer baseline segments between the three fixed VLBI stations.

4.2 SEA LEVEL OPERATIONS

A number of problems exist with the presently deployed tides/sea level measurement technology. The existing float-in-well measurement systems and paper punch tape recording technologies are subject to reliability, accuracy and time resolution problems which make the value of "sea level" determinations obtained at any one location questionable. In fact, it is only when a large enough ensemble of measurement series over a large region or global area are averaged that long-term trends so determined have any credibility.

The systems now in use in the NWLON record a single sample every six minutes. The float operates in a well with a small orifice (a "stilling" well). The stilling well acts as a frequency dependent mechanical filter for the high frequency wave effects. However, these high frequency effects of the sea surface are not all filtered out and the stilling well is

subject to density gradients affecting the float, wave buildup effects, bio-fouling, etc. The narrow orifices of the stilling wells are particularly subject to hydrodynamic "draw down" effects wherever there is a significant ambient current. The float system also has inertial response problems and experiences gradual buoyancy changes. The poor temporal resolution of the measurements can be dealt with by using relatively sophisticated shaft-angle encoding devices currently available, but these may introduce unknown systematic errors and do nothing to deal with the known systematic errors inherent in the float and stilling well device itself.

As it stands, the accuracy for a single measurement of the sea surface using existing NWLON technology cannot be considered to be better than about 10cm. Much of this error is due to nearly random effects of the high frequency signals (waves) that can be statistically reduced from the very long term signals in multi-year time series, so that long term trends of a few millimeters per year can be extracted from the data. However, to the extent that the other errors cited introduce "systematic" errors that are not random and cannot be statistically removed, they may leave small amplitude, long-period effects virtually indistinguishable (without some independent method of determining them) from the sea level trends. These possible remaining long period systematic errors can only be dealt with, if at all, by averaging measurements from many gauges, widely distributed geographically. It should be noted that effects like hydrodynamic drawdown, which are always ≥ 0 , will never be entirely removed by simple averaging methods, even over a large ensemble of gauges.

For all of the reasons cited above, any rigorous approach to determining the regional sea level response over an area like the East Coast of the United States, exhibiting as much local variation as is shown in Figure 1, requires that the technical problems related to the accurate measurement of the sea surface be dealt with. The SLEEC methodology addresses these problems.

NOS is developing a Next Generation Water Levels Measurement System (NGWLMS). The NGWLMS concept is a total systems approach, from the water surface measurement (now to employ a remote acoustic sensor) through the data recording, transmission, and data processing. Near real-time data collection and transmission will allow greatly improved quality control procedures. The requirement for accurate and reliable long-term sea level measurements has been factored into the NGWLMS system requirements. These requirements support the needs of marine boundary applications, as well as the climate and related applications. The new NGWLMS system will also include the capability for a suite of colocated auxiliary meteorological and oceanographic measurement systems vital for distinguishing and analyzing the

various subtle contributions to the "sea level" signal.

By replacing the float with a non-mechanical acoustic sensor not involving the physical contact of a device, such as a float, with the water surface, a large number of sources of systematic errors are either eliminated, or greatly reduced. There is no longer any need for a narrow orifice mechanical filter in the form of a stilling well, so that this is replaced by an open protective well, much less subject to draw down and biofouling, not conducive to density gradient buildups and more indicative of the outside ocean environment. The acoustic signal can be transmitted in a series of rapid pulses, so that whereas the old system provided one 6-minute sample, the NGWLMS measurement will involve averaging 180 samples over the same period of time and computing measurement statistics as well.

Acoustic systems are subject to known temperature dependent effects. However, the NGWLMS will include temperature measurements as part of the basic measurement suite, allowing for post-measurement correction of any remaining uncalibrated temperature related errors. Actually, temperature is recorded at a number of positions at the installation to provide the basis for automated temperature corrections at the DCP (self calibration). The measurements of the ambient air and water temperatures are in addition to these engineering measurements. The suite of ancillary environmental measurements intended for the master sea level stations proposed for SLEEC will allow analysis and elimination of any environmentally induced systematic errors that may still remain in the measurements, such as residual draw down in the protective well. However, this is not the main reason for including the ancillary measurement systems in SLEEC: they are necessary for supporting the analysis of the sea level data.

The electronic data recording and transmission of the NGWLMS, replacing the manually collected and transmitted paper punch tape of the old systems, eliminates a whole series of errors incurred during that phase of the operations. The NGWLMS also self-reports, in near real-time, a set of operational status parameters and system diagnostics essential to data quality operations.

The prototype NGWLMS system is now undergoing testing. Based on the design specifications and initial test results, the single NGWLMS measurement from NGWLMS should represent an order of magnitude improvement over the existing measurement type, i.e., the single measurement will be good to the ± 1 cm level, with most all of the known systematic error effects removed. This is consistent with the expectations for the single measurements from the geodetic systems.

Assuming that the ± 1 cm level of accuracy for both the geodetic measurements and the water levels measurements is largely limited by

remaining errors of a random nature, then the total system error for SLEEC, on the basis of a single measurement of the true sea level, can be approximated by the root mean square (RMS) error for the sum of the geodetic and water levels measurements, or about 1.4 cm. current global analyses suggest that the true sea level trend is in the neighborhood of 1-2mm per year. A 2 mm/year trend continued over a decade produces a 2cm effect, which is well above the expected noise level of the measurements and should be readily observable. Therefore, the trends of the land and water levels at an individual station should be accurately determined within 5-10 years. However, in an average sense for the entire East Coast, the eleven master sea level stations should statistically reduce the overall measurement noise by about a factor of three, so that 1-2 mm/year land subsidence or sea level rise trends may be resolved, separately, after about 3 years of operation.

It also should be noted that possibilities exist for refining the accuracies of the geodetic measurement to about the 0.5cm level. In this case, the total RMS system error would drop to about 1cm for a single observation. At the present time, the accuracy of the geodetic measurements are the limiting influence on the length of time series needed to statistically recover long period trends of small amplitude, since the water levels measurements can be made much more frequently than the geodetic measurements, thus providing greater statistical reduction of the noise in the signal processing.

Measuring the absolute or true rise of sea level along the East Coast of the United States is one thing. Analyzing and interpreting the results is another. This is where the real contribution of the ancillary measurement systems, to be colocated at the master sea level stations along with the basic NGWLMS water levels measurement technology, make their major contribution.

If a component of true sea level rise distinguishable from land or local effects is measured at a number of stations along the entire East Coast of the U.S., it cannot be immediately concluded that this is due to an inexorable "eustatic" rise in the global oceans, destined to persist, or even accelerate, over many centuries. Much less can it be causally related to the observed increase in atmospheric CO₂ and other trace gases, without more information. Many things may be affecting sea level rise along the East Coast, even on time scales of decades or centuries. Natural major variability in the atmosphere and oceans due to climate changes on the scale of several or more decades is now known to exist. This may include shifts in the oceanic circulation manifested in upwelling effects near the coast, shifts in major ocean boundary currents (i.e., the Gulf Stream), shifts in the positions of the major high and low pressure centers in the atmosphere and related major wind systems, changes in precipitation patterns and levels, river runoff, etc.

Such effects, even if persistent for many decades over nearly continental sized areas, might "turn around" producing an opposite effect within a few decades. They might also run counter-to or even enhance any actual very-long term trend. The nature and effects of some of these mechanisms could be unravelled with the help of general circulation models, but not without use of, and supporting analyses based on, real data. The ancillary measurement systems will provide some of the needed data, for the first time, in continuous time series colocated with the sea level measurements. The standard measurements will include air and water temperatures, wind velocity and barometric pressures. Selected sites may have additional sensors for ocean current speeds or velocities, and salinity or conductivity, if local conditions warrant their installation. Needless to say, the implications for coastal policies of the kind of information to be provided by the ancillary measurement systems are very substantial.

The SLEEC concept will involve establishment of eleven master sea level stations at sites on the East Coast between Florida and Maine so that three or four stations are placed along the length of coast line corresponding to each segment of the relative sea level profile shown in Figure 1. As previously noted, these sea level stations will be geodetically tied in with GPS geodetic station points. The sites of the eleven master sea level stations are given in Table 1.

NOS has prototype NGWLMS units installed at five of these sites. Four of the stations have the ancillary sensors installed. All of the NOS National Water Levels Observation Network (NWLON) eventually will be converted to the production version of the NGWLMS by the mid 1990's, but in order to support SLEEC, early installation of the prototype NGWLMS system, including the ancillary sensors, will be needed at the remaining six sites prior to the scheduled operational conversion of the network. It will be important to start the ancillary oceanographic and meteorological time series at the same time as the water level measurements with the NGWLMS. NOAA is working toward establishing the basic system and anticipates working with other Federal agencies to support the multi-year funding required to continue SLEEC and the Global Sea Level Monitoring effort.

5.0 REFERENCES

1. D. Aubrey and K. O. Emery; Continental Shelf Research, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 21-23, 1983.

Figure 1. Relative Sea Level Rise Along the East Coast of the United States with Monitoring Station Locations for SLEEC